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A Survey of Audiences' Motivation to Attend Cantonese Opera Performances in Hong Kong

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Abstract: *Cantonese opera is a traditional Chinese opera genre popular in Hong Kong since the late nineteenth century. However, the genre has faced declining audience attendance in recent decades, despite promotion by Hong Kong government through various channels. There is a dearth of research on factors shaping audience motivation to attend live performances of this genre. This article reports an investigation of audience motivations to attend Cantonese opera performances using an online survey in Hong Kong. A total of 3,447 valid questionnaires were collected while MANOVA and ANOVA methods were used in the data analysis. Significant factors determining audience attendance included the intrinsic value of the performance, the quality of the artists, the quality of the performance venue, and an appropriate performance duration. While artists should strive for continuous improvement, the duration of performances might need to be shortened to suit attendees' busy schedules.*

Keywords: *Cantonese opera, marketing for arts, audience motivation, Hong Kong*

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1. Introduction

Cantonese opera was recognized as an essential part of cultural heritage when it was listed on the first national register of Intangible Cultural Heritage in 2006 and subsequently included in UNESCO's Representative List of Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity in 2009 [1]. This traditional art form enjoys significant popularity in Hong Kong and Guangdong [2].

Despite the existing marketing research into audience motivations for attending various artistic performances, there is a notable lack of studies focused specifically on Cantonese opera. Gaining a deeper understanding of why audiences choose to attend these performances could enhance attendance rates, support the preservation of this traditional genre, and foster the artistic development of performers. Key questions addressed by this study include: How do audiences in Hong Kong decide which performances to attend? What factors influence their attendance decisions? To explore these questions, we conducted a large-scale online survey targeting both attendees and non-attendees of Cantonese opera. Insights into the preferences and expectations of current and potential audiences can guide cultural managers, producers, educators, government officials, and other stakeholders in improving cultural offerings and ultimately increasing attendance.

2. Objectives

The primary objectives of this study were to: 1) explore the perspectives and motivations of Hong Kong audiences regarding Cantonese opera performances and related concerts, and 2) offer valuable insights to policymakers and producers to help broaden and expand the audience base for Cantonese opera.

Two key research questions directed this inquiry:

1. What factors influence audiences' motivations to attend Cantonese opera performances?
2. How do the various proposed factors relate to one another?

3. Theoretical Framework on Motivation

Previous studies have outlined numerous motivations driving audiences to engage in cultural activities. Self-determination theory (SDT) sheds light on the underlying motivations behind choices made without external pressures [3], highlighting the extent to which individuals are self-motivated. SDT categorizes motivation into three types: intrinsic, extrinsic, and amotivation [4].

Intrinsic motivation refers to engaging in an activity for personal enjoyment and satisfaction, rather than for external rewards or constraints [3]. Conversely, extrinsic motivation is characterized by behavior driven by external outcomes rather than the activity

itself. A person may initially attend a performance for external reasons (e.g., to see a well-known artist) but may eventually find intrinsic motivation that complements the initial external motivator, leading to a shift from extrinsic to intrinsic motivation [4].

Amotivation, on the other hand, indicates a lack of motivation, where individuals may feel uncertain about the outcomes of their actions and may even opt not to engage in an activity. For example, in this study's context, amotivated individuals might attend a cultural performance solely because they are accompanying others [4].

The Theory of Cognitive Evaluation (TCE), developed by Deci [5] and later expanded by Deci and Ryan [6], examines how intrinsic motivation evolves under the influence of environmental factors. Research has indicated that individuals' perceived competence significantly enhances their intrinsic motivation [7]. Environmental factors, including marketing communication and informational events, can serve as tools to enhance intrinsic motivation and foster positive attitudes towards an activity [8] [9]. A high level of knowledge about an activity can also sustain participation over time, as opposed to discouraging it [10]. Therefore, fostering intrinsic motivation can lead to sustained engagement with an activity [11].

Obaidalahe and Steils [4] utilized the motivation continuum from Deci and Ryan [3] to suggest that increased knowledge can transform amotivation into extrinsic and even intrinsic motivation. This shift in audience motivation holds significant managerial implications; while motivation is inherently personal, cultural institutions can enhance audience knowledge through effective communication strategies. The authors also investigated sustainable approaches for cultural managers to attract visitors based on intrinsic motivation [4].

3.1. Individual Characteristics

Moving beyond traditional socio-demographic factors, Roose [12] examined how individual characteristics, such as aesthetic dispositions and motivations for attending classical concerts, can influence audience behavior. This research builds upon a well-established tradition in aesthetic experience analysis [13] [14] [15] [16].

Research into the internal stratification of arts audiences dates back to Becker [17], who identified distinct groups with unique traits and preferences among arts consumers. The core audience typically comprises individuals professionally involved in the arts, who attend more frequently and encourage innovative experimentation. This group serves as both a sounding board for artists and a cautionary presence for less experienced audiences, being well-versed in the conventions of the genre and open to new styles.

A secondary audience consists of less frequent attendees who may lack formal training yet are interested and informed, forming a substantial social and economic base for arts production. The third segment includes students of the arts, overlapping with the previous

groups. Becker's segmentation is based on factors such as professional involvement, experience with the arts, and knowledge of the art form's conventions.

Laermans [18] offered a similar segmentation model, identifying three circles of arts audiences: a core group, a second circle of interested participants, and a third circle of incidental visitors, many of whom attend sporadically for reasons unrelated to genuine artistic interest.

3.2. Attendance Segmentation Variables

According to Kolhede and Gomez-Arias [19], attendance segmentation variables can be summarized as follows.

3.2.1. Behavioral and Demographic Segmentation: Findings regarding the predictability of performing arts attendance based on demographic factors are often conflicting. For instance, Kolb [20], Andreasen and Belk [21], and [22] Boerner et. al. [23] concluded that gender is an ineffective variable for predicting attendance and patron expectations, challenging the stereotype that performance art audiences are predominantly female. Davis and Swanson [24] argued that demographic segmentation of regular patrons may not yield useful insights, as consumer profiles often show similarities.

To develop comprehensive audience profiles, socio-economic variables are more accurate predictors of performing arts attendance when combined with other factors that reflect purchasing behavior [20] [21] [25]. Some studies advocate for a multidimensional approach to audience profiling, highlighting the need to consider various factors, including consumer assessments of service quality, commitment to performing arts organizations, and social influences impacting attitudes toward the arts.

3.2.2. Service Quality Attributes: Research has explored the significance of service quality attributes for both general consumers [26] and arts consumers, establishing these factors as antecedents of behavioral intentions and actual outcomes. Service quality encompasses both the core service—elements of the artistic performance—and peripheral services, including ticket purchasing ease, usher friendliness, parking availability, and opportunities for social interaction at events [23].

Hume and Mort [27] noted that arts organizations often prioritize core artistic elements while neglecting peripheral aspects. Patrons evaluate both core and peripheral service elements, and their satisfaction is influenced by the gap between expectations and actual experiences [28]. Studies indicate that all performing arts patrons prioritize core services, regardless of attendance frequency [29] [30], with emotional benefits, including escapism, serving as a key motivator for attending [12] [23]. However, core services hold greater significance for highly engaged patrons compared to infrequent attendees, who may

focus more on peripheral services like venue atmosphere and social opportunities [31] [32].

Evidence regarding the role of consumer perceptions of service quality as a segmentation variable and predictor of satisfaction remains mixed. Boerner et. al. [23] found that perceptions of peripheral service quality did not significantly impact satisfaction among opera attendees, regardless of attendance frequency. They reported that service quality was not a significant determinant of satisfaction for theater patrons.

3.2.3. Social Influences. Social influences have been examined in the context of arts patron profiles, focusing on two primary areas: early developmental experiences, including formal arts education and family influences, and the impact of reference groups on decision-making.

Positive arts education and socialization during childhood and adolescence significantly shape long-term attendance predispositions [33] [34] [35]. Therefore, performing arts organizations should implement arts education programs to cultivate future audiences [21] [29] [33]. Espinola and Badrinarayanan [33] emphasized the role of arts education in maintaining expertise, which can bolster behavioral motivations to attend arts events. Moreover, arts education enhances cognitive abilities to remember and analyze art forms, potentially fostering enthusiasm and a desire for further knowledge, leading to sustained engagement.

Shoham and Brencic [34] portrayed the core audience of a performing arts organization as older patrons motivated by internal values such as self-respect and fulfillment rather than social approval. While they appreciate group connections, their attendance is driven more by personal than social benefits. In contrast, occasional attendees tend to be younger and more susceptible to social influences, often motivated by the social aspects of attending events. Arts managers could target less engaged individuals through their social networks [21] [34].

4. Methodology

4.1. Questionnaire Design

The research team developed a bilingual questionnaire in Chinese and English, consisting of three parts. Part I gathered demographic information, including six dependent variables: gender, age, education level, monthly household income, employment status, and frequency of Cantonese opera attendance. Participants were categorized into gender groups, age brackets (under 30, 31-59, 60 and above), education levels (secondary and below, undergraduate, postgraduate), employment status (full-time, part-time, retired/unemployed/housewife, full-time student), and monthly attendance frequency (0, 1-3, 4 or more).

Part II focused on the views and motivations of Hong Kong audiences regarding Cantonese opera performances and related concerts, utilizing nine independent variables measured through 36 statements on a 7-point semantic differential scale (1 = “strongly disagree,” 7 = “strongly agree”). The nine dimensions included:

1. Personal motivators: Six statements addressing personal reasons for attending performances, such as supporting Hong Kong Cantonese opera and personal enjoyment.
2. Promotion motivators: Five statements exploring the significance of various marketing methods, including advertising and referrals.
3. Distribution motivators: Six statements relating to performance accessibility, such as proximity to restaurants and public transportation.
4. Performance quality: Three statements assessing the quality of performances and the cast.
5. Performance content: Seven statements focusing on the content and familiarity of the performances.
6. Environmental motivators: Three statements addressing venue attractiveness and suitability.
7. Time motivators: Two statements regarding the duration of performances.
8. Economic motivators: Two statements concerning ticket pricing.
9. Social motivators: Two statements exploring social motivations for attending.

Part III included two open-ended questions: “What other reasons do you have for attending a performance?” and “What is your primary reason for deciding to purchase a ticket?” The first question aimed to uncover additional factors influencing attendance beyond the nine motivators identified in the study.

4.2. Participants

The study included 3,447 participants (27% male, 73% female; 29.1% aged 30 or under, 34.8% aged 31-59, and 36.1% aged 60 and above), representing diverse educational backgrounds (29.5% secondary or below, 46.9% undergraduate, and 23.6% postgraduate) and employment statuses (43.5% full-time, 10.3% part-time, 32.5% non-working, and 13.7% full-time students).

4.3. Procedure

The research team conducted a pilot test with approximately 100 participants and adjusted based on feedback before launching the online survey in March 2022. Data collection concluded on June 30, 2022. The survey targeted all Hong Kong residents aged 18 and older, utilizing snowball sampling and leveraging personal networks. Participants were recruited through emails, social media, and connections within the Cantonese opera community. To

encourage participation, respondents had the chance to enter a lottery for one of 75 HKD 200 supermarket coupons. The lottery was conducted in October 2022.

The questionnaire was adapted from the framework established by Kolhede and Gomez-Arias [19], incorporating factors relevant to the Cantonese opera context. The survey included demographic information and a 36-item scale assessing factors influencing attendance, categorized into personal, advertising, availability, performance quality, content, venue, time, economic, and social motivators, utilizing a 7-point scale for participant responses.

4.4. Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics summarized the importance of each factor and the influence of demographic variables on attendance. The psychometric properties of the nine-factor scale were assessed for reliability, including inter-correlations and individual Cronbach's α . A confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was performed using the 'lavaan' package in R [35], comparing the fit of a one-factor and a nine-factor model. Missing data were addressed using full information maximum likelihood.

General factor profile differences across demographic groups were explored using MANOVA with Pillai's trace, followed by ANOVA for significant differences. Effect sizes were calculated with partial eta-squared (η_p^2). The relationships between attendance and demographic variables, along with the nine influencing factors, were analyzed using Cramér's V (ϕ_c) and Pearson correlation (r). Ordinal regression was employed to assess the individual contributions of demographic variables and influencing factors to attendance.

5. Results

Overall, performance quality (mean = 5.02, s.d. = 1.52) emerged as the most significant factor impacting attendance across demographic groups, with notable consistency among sex, age, education level, and employment status. For full-time students, performance content was identified as the primary motivator. Table 1 presents the mean scores and standard deviations of all factors, along with monthly attendance figures across demographic categories.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of nine factors and number of attendances of Cantonese opera per month

Sample	Factor (Mean score and standard deviation in a 5-point scale)									No. of Cantonese opera attendance (per month) (Frequency and percentage)		
	1. Personal	2. Promotion	3. Distribution	4. Performance quality	5. Performance content	6. Venue	7. Time	8. Economic	9. Social	0	1 to 3	4 or above
Total (N=3447)	4.49 (1.49)	3.93 (1.38)	4.23 (1.44)	5.02 (1.52)	4.64 (1.19)	4.37 (1.3)	3.83 (1.66)	4.24 (1.28)	3.01 (1.67)	1955 (56.7)	1132 (32.8)	360 (10.4)
Sex												
Male (N=930)	4.29 (1.52)	3.74 (1.43)	4 (1.47)	4.77 (1.59)	4.52 (1.26)	4.25 (1.36)	3.96 (1.62)	4.2 (1.31)	3.04 (1.7)	519 (55.81)	316 (33.98)	95 (10.22)
Female (N=2517)	4.56 (1.47)	4 (1.36)	4.31 (1.42)	5.11 (1.49)	4.69 (1.16)	4.42 (1.27)	3.78 (1.67)	4.26 (1.26)	3 (1.66)	1436 (57.05)	816 (32.42)	265 (10.53)
Age												
30 or below (N=1002)	3.78 (1.41)	3.7 (1.37)	3.8 (1.42)	4.09 (1.48)	4.52 (1.33)	4.06 (1.39)	4.07 (1.55)	4.09 (1.25)	3.05 (1.61)	807 (80.5)	161 (16.1)	34 (3.4)
31 to 59 (N=1199)	4.38 (1.45)	3.98 (1.39)	4.3 (1.44)	5.05 (1.47)	4.65 (1.17)	4.42 (1.24)	3.92 (1.67)	4.17 (1.26)	3.12 (1.7)	772 (64.39)	339 (28.27)	88 (7.34)
60 or above (N=1246)	5.16 (1.28)	4.07 (1.36)	4.51 (1.38)	5.73 (1.18)	4.74 (1.07)	4.58 (1.22)	3.54 (1.69)	4.43 (1.29)	2.87 (1.68)	376 (30.2)	632 (50.7)	238 (19.1)
Educational level												
Below secondary (N=1018)	5.09 (1.41)	4.09 (1.4)	4.5 (1.44)	5.61 (1.36)	4.72 (1.14)	4.66 (1.27)	3.44 (1.73)	4.3 (1.35)	2.87 (1.69)	353 (34.68)	480 (47.15)	185 (18.17)
Undergraduate (N=1617)	4.16 (1.48)	3.86 (1.36)	4.07 (1.42)	4.69 (1.55)	4.58 (1.26)	4.22 (1.31)	3.97 (1.6)	4.17 (1.23)	3.1 (1.64)	1083 (66.98)	423 (26.16)	111 (6.86)
Postgraduate (N=812)	4.39 (1.37)	3.87 (1.38)	4.2 (1.44)	4.92 (1.43)	4.67 (1.11)	4.32 (1.23)	4.02 (1.61)	4.3 (1.26)	2.98 (1.69)	519 (63.92)	229 (28.2)	64 (7.88)
Working status												
Full-time (N=1500)	4.22 (1.49)	3.82 (1.41)	4.1 (1.46)	4.77 (1.55)	4.56 (1.23)	4.23 (1.32)	3.96 (1.66)	4.16 (1.28)	3.07 (1.66)	1016 (67.73)	373 (24.87)	111 (7.4)
Part-time (N=356)	4.53 (1.4)	3.9 (1.3)	4.24 (1.41)	4.99 (1.47)	4.62 (1.17)	4.45 (1.25)	3.74 (1.63)	4.22 (1.24)	2.95 (1.62)	194 (54.49)	123 (34.55)	39 (10.96)
Non-working (N=1120)	5.1 (1.33)	4.14 (1.36)	4.56 (1.37)	5.7 (1.22)	4.77 (1.07)	4.62 (1.21)	3.56 (1.7)	4.38 (1.28)	2.9 (1.72)	366 (32.68)	553 (49.38)	201 (17.95)

Table 2 details the inter-correlations among the nine factors and their respective Cronbach’s α . Strong correlations ($r_s > .5$) were observed among personal, advertising, distribution, performance quality, performance content, and venue factors, with moderate correlations with economic factors ($r_s > .3$). The correlation between time and other factors was weak ($r_s < .3$), while the social factor showed moderate correlations with advertising, availability, and venue ($r_s > .3$). Most scales exhibited acceptable reliability ($\alpha > .7$), except for the venue ($\alpha = .65$). CFA results indicated a marginally adequate fit for the nine-factor structure ($\chi^2 (558) = 9063.45, p < .001$; RMSEA = .077; CFI = .840; TLI = .819; SRMR = .067), outperforming the one-factor model ($\Delta\chi^2 (36) = 10676.00, p < .001$).

Table 2. Inter-correlation of nine factors and their reliabilities

Factor	Me	S.	α	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
	an	D.									
1. Personal	4.4	1.4	.8	-							
	9	9	3								

2. Promotion	3.9 3	1.3 8	.8 3	.51* **	-						
3. Distribution	4.2 3	1.4 4	.8 8	.51* **	.62* **	-					
4. Performance quality	5.0 2	1.5 2	.8 6	.69* **	.45* **	.53* **	-				
5. Performance content	4.6 4	1.1 9	.8 5	.54* **	.58* **	.56* **	.56* **	-			
6. Environment	4.3 7	1.3 0	.6 5	.58* **	.54* **	.61* **	.59* **	.64* **	-		
7. Time	3.8 3	1.6 6	.8 5	-.18* **	.10* **	.07* *	-.11* **	.04* **	.00	-	
8. Economic	4.2 4	1.2 8	.7 1	.43* **	.38* **	.37* **	.41* **	.44* **	.49* **	.10* **	-
9. Social	3.0 1	1.6 7	.9 1	.11* **	.42* **	.34* **	.10* **	.28* **	.30* **	.27* **	.21* **

Table 3 summarizes MANOVA results, revealing significant profile differences across demographic groups (for sex, Pillai's trace = .018, $F(9, 3437) = 6.87$, $p < .001$; for age, Pillai's trace = .277, $F(18, 6874) = 61.32$, $p < .001$; for education level, Pillai's trace = .122, $F(18, 6874) = 25.34$, $p < .001$; for working status, Pillai's trace = .179, $F(27, 10311) = 24.08$, $p < .001$). Age demonstrated a strong effect size ($\eta_p^2 = .138$), while education level ($\eta_p^2 = .062$) and working status ($\eta_p^2 = .138$) showed moderate effects. The effect size for sex was small ($\eta_p^2 = .018$). ANOVA results indicated significant differences ($p < .001$) across demographic groups for nearly all factors, except for economic ($p = .246$) and social factors ($p = .510$) among sexes (see Table 4). Performance quality exhibited the largest variation across different demographic factors (for sex, $\eta_p^2 = .010$; for age, $\eta_p^2 = .186$; for working status, $\eta_p^2 = .119$), while the personal factor showed the most significant differences across education levels ($\eta_p^2 = .072$).

Table 3. MANOVA on general factor profile across demographic groups

Independent variable	Pillai's trace	F	df 1	df 2	p	η_p^2
Sex	0.018	6.87	9	3437	<.001	0018

Age	0.277	61.32	18	6874	<.001	.138
Education level	0.122	25.34	18	6874	<.001	.062
Working status	0.179	24.08	27	10311	<.001	.059

Table 4. ANOVA on individual factor across demographic groups

Factor	Mean (S.D.)				ANOVA		
					Welch's statistic	p	η_p^2
By Sex	Male	Female					
1. Personal	4.29 (1.52)	4.56 (1.47)			22.72	<.001	.007
2. Advertising	3.74 (1.43)	4 (1.36)			23.44	<.001	.007
3. Distribution	4 (1.47)	4.31 (1.42)			30.07	<.001	.009
4. Performance quality	4.77 (1.59)	5.11 (1.49)			31.83	<.001	.010
5. Performance content	4.52 (1.26)	4.69 (1.16)			12.17	<.001	.004
6. Venue	4.25 (1.36)	4.42 (1.27)			11.52	.001	.004
7. Time	3.96 (1.62)	3.78 (1.67)			8.71	.003	.002
8. Economical	4.2 (1.31)	4.26 (1.26)			1.34	.246	.000
9. Social	3.04 (1.7)	3 (1.66)			0.43	.51	.000
By Age	30 or below	31 to 59	60 or above				
1. Personal	3.78 (1.41)	4.38 (1.45)	5.16 (1.28)		298.97	<.001	.141
2. Advertising	3.7 (1.37)	3.98 (1.39)	4.07 (1.36)		22.02	<.001	.012
3. Distribution	3.8 (1.42)	4.3 (1.44)	4.51 (1.38)		72.94	<.001	.040
4. Performance quality	4.09 (1.48)	5.05 (1.47)	5.73 (1.18)		407.73	<.001	.186
5. Performance content	4.52 (1.33)	4.65 (1.17)	4.74 (1.07)		8.86	<.001	.005
6. Venue	4.06 (1.39)	4.42 (1.24)	4.58 (1.22)		44.74	<.001	.027
7. Time	4.07 (1.55)	3.92 (1.67)	3.54 (1.69)		32.6	<.001	.018
8. Economical	4.09 (1.25)	4.17 (1.26)	4.43 (1.29)		23.01	<.001	.013
9. Social	3.05 (1.61)	3.12 (1.7)	2.87 (1.68)		7.31	.001	.004
By Educational level	Below secondary	Undergraduate	Postgraduate				
1. Personal	5.09 (1.41)	4.16 (1.48)	4.39 (1.37)		134.41	<.001	.072
2. Advertising	4.09 (1.4)	3.86 (1.36)	3.87 (1.38)		10.16	<.001	.006
3. Distribution	4.5 (1.44)	4.07 (1.42)	4.2 (1.44)		29.2	<.001	.017
4. Performance quality	5.61 (1.36)	4.69 (1.55)	4.92 (1.43)		132.29	<.001	.067
5. Performance content	4.72 (1.14)	4.58 (1.26)	4.67 (1.11)		4.88	.008	.003
6. Venue	4.66 (1.27)	4.22 (1.31)	4.32 (1.23)		37.27	<.001	.021
7. Time	3.44 (1.73)	3.97 (1.6)	4.02 (1.61)		37.96	<.001	.023
8. Economical	4.3 (1.35)	4.17 (1.23)	4.3 (1.26)		4.35	.013	.002
9. Social	2.87 (1.69)	3.1 (1.64)	2.98 (1.69)		6.18	.002	.004
By Working status	Full-time	Part-time	Non-working	Full-time student			
1. Personal	4.22 (1.49)	4.53 (1.4)	5.1 (1.33)	3.85 (1.38)	127.17	<.001	.094
2. Advertising	3.82 (1.41)	3.9 (1.3)	4.14 (1.36)	3.8 (1.35)	12.89	<.001	.011
3. Distribution	4.1 (1.46)	4.24 (1.41)	4.56 (1.37)	3.85 (1.42)	36.5	<.001	.030
4. Performance quality	4.77 (1.55)	4.99 (1.47)	5.7 (1.22)	4.18 (1.48)	175.48	<.001	.119
5. Performance content	4.56 (1.23)	4.62 (1.17)	4.77 (1.07)	4.61 (1.31)	7.44	<.001	.006
6. Venue	4.23 (1.32)	4.45 (1.25)	4.62 (1.21)	4.19 (1.35)	24.31	<.001	.020
7. Time	3.96 (1.66)	3.74 (1.63)	3.56 (1.7)	4.09 (1.51)	17.77	<.001	.015

Associations between attendance and demographic variables, as well as the influencing factors, are summarized in Table 5. Significant associations were found for age, education level, and working status (for age, $\phi_c = .30$, $p < .001$; for education level, $\phi_c = .21$, $p < .001$; for working status, $\phi_c = .26$, $p < .001$), but not for sex ($\phi_c = .02$, $p = .687$). All relationships among the nine factors were significant ($ps < .01$), with moderate associations for personal factors ($rs = .47$) and performance quality ($rs = .40$). Associations with time ($rs = -.20$) and social factors ($rs = -.05$) were weakly negative.

Table 5. Association of Cantonese opera attendance with demographic groups and nine factors

Variable	Correlation coefficient#	p
Demographic variable		
Sex	.02	.687
Age	.30	<.001
Education level	.21	<.001
Working status	.26	<.001
Factor		
1. Personal	.47	<.001
2. Advertising	.14	<.001
3. Distribution	.17	<.001
4. Performance quality	.4	<.001
5. Performance content	.17	<.001
6. Venue	.25	<.001
7. Time	-0.2	<.001
8. Economical	.17	<.001
9. Social	-0.05	.008

For demographic variables, Cramér's V (ϕ_c) was adopted for nominal association, for the nine factors, Pearson correlation (r) were adopted.

To assess the individual contributions of variables toward attendance, ordinal regression was conducted. The model's regression coefficients significantly differed from zero ($\chi^2(17) = 1382.61$, $p < .001$), demonstrating an adequate fit (deviance test, $\chi^2(6817) = 4973.04$, $p = 1.000$). The model explained moderate variation in the dependent variable (Nagelkerke $R^2 = .392$).

Table 6 presents the regression results. Males showed a higher likelihood of attending Cantonese opera (for females, $B = -.265$, $p = .002$), while attendees aged 60 and above had increased attendance ($B = .867$, $p < .001$). Higher education levels correlated with decreased attendance (for undergraduates, $B = -.369$, $p < .001$; for postgraduates, $B = -.419$, $p < .001$). Non-working individuals attended more frequently than full-time workers ($B = .288$, $p = .011$). Factors positively related to attendance included personal motivations ($B = .626$, $p < .001$), performance quality ($B = .258$, $p < .001$), and venue ($B = .138$, $p = .003$). Conversely, availability ($B = -.138$, $p < .001$), performance content ($B = -.151$, $p = .002$), and time ($B = -.115$, $p < .001$) were negatively associated.

Table 6. Ordinal regression of Cantonese opera attendance on demographic groups and nine factors

Independent variable	Ordinal regression						
	Estimate (B)	s.e.	Wald	df	p	exp (B)	95% C.I. of exp(B)
Demographic group							
[Sex = "Male"]	0	-	-	-	-		
[Sex = "Female"]	-.265	.087	9.218	1	.002	.767	[.646, .91]
[Age = "30 or below"]	0	-	-	-	-		
[Age = "31 to 59"]	.185	.138	1.812	1	.178	1.204	[.919 ,1.577]
[Age = "60 or above"]	.867	.159	29.611	1	.000	2.381	[1.742 ,3.254]
[Education level = "Below secondary"]	0	-	-	-	-		
[Education level = "Undergraduate"]	-.369	.095	15.110	1	.000	.692	[.574 ,.833]
[Education level = "Postgraduate"]	-.419	.107	15.255	1	.000	.658	[.533 ,.812]
[Working status = "Full-time"]	0	-	-	-	-		
[Working status = "Part-time"]	.232	.133	3.059	1	.080	1.261	[.972 ,1.636]
[Working status = "Non-working"]	.288	.113	6.445	1	.011	1.334	[1.068 ,1.666]
[Working status = "Full-	-.125	.115	.537	1	.464	.883	[.632 ,1.233]

Factor							
time student"]		70			64]
1. Personal	.626	.0 42	218. 727	1	.0 00	1.87 0	[1.721 ,2.03 2]
2. Advertising	-.056	.0 40	2.00 6	1	.1 57	.945	[.874 ,1.022]
3. Availability	-.138	.0 39	12.7 36	1	.0 00	.871	[.807 ,.94]
4. Performance quality	.258	.0 42	38.1 86	1	.0 00	1.29 5	[1.193 ,1.40 5]
5. Performance content	-.151	.0 50	9.29 0	1	.0 02	.859	[.780 ,.947]
6. Venue	.138	.0 46	9.12 6	1	.0 03	1.14 8	[1.05 ,1.255]
7. Time	-.115	.0 25	21.3 27	1	.0 00	.891	[.849 ,.936]
8. Economical	.002	.0 35	.002	1	.9 61	1.00 2	[.934 ,1.074]
9. Social	.012	.0 26	.193	1	.6 61	1.01 2	[.961 ,1.065]

Out of 3,447 valid survey responses, 1,753 (50.9% response rate) addressed the open-ended question on additional reasons for ticket purchases. Many participants reiterated the proposed motivators in this study:

1. Personal motivators (e.g., supporting Hong Kong Cantonese opera, personal cultural enrichment) constituted 21.5% of responses (377/1,753).
2. Quality of performance (e.g., the cast) accounted for 17.7% of responses (311/1,753).
3. Social motivators (e.g., social gatherings, accompanying friends/family) represented 16.3% of valid responses (286/1,753).

Only 26 answers suggested reasons outside the proposed motivators, including:

1. Weather Conditions: Older audience members may hesitate to attend outdoor performances in poor weather.
2. Pre- and Post-Performance Activities: Novice attendees might benefit from more information about Cantonese opera, such as guided tours that provide context for the performances.

3. **Pandemic Measures:** The study occurred during the COVID-19 pandemic, during which various restrictions influenced ticket purchasing decisions, including vaccination requirements for venue entry.

A 63.2% response rate (2,178 out of 3,447) was achieved for the open-ended question on ticket purchase motivations. Participants echoed the proposed reasons: personal motivators (565 responses, 25.9%), quality of performance (514 responses, 23.6%), and product motivators (360 responses, 16.5%) were the most frequently cited reasons.

6. Discussion

6.1. Importance of Performance Quality, Content, and Personal Motivators

The findings indicate that performance quality is the foremost factor influencing attendees' decisions to purchase tickets for Cantonese opera. Participants aged 60 and older rated performance quality highly (mean score of 5.73), as did non-working participants (mean score of 5.7). In this study, performance quality encompassed the overall quality of the cast. Additionally, performance content, including the types of performances and well-known plays, emerged as significant motivators. Personal motivators were particularly important for attendees aged 60 and above and non-working individuals.

Cultural offerings are critically important to highly engaged attendees, such as regular ticket buyers, whose intrinsic interest in performance offerings drives their attendance [12] [24] [31]. The results suggest that cultural managers should prioritize maintaining high performance quality and tailoring content to suit target audiences, thereby encouraging ticket purchases. Artistic directors of Cantonese opera organizations should regularly assess audience expectations regarding quality and design offerings that align with these expectations.

Engaging Non-Attendees and Potential Attendees Through Education

A lack of relevant educational opportunities may contribute to declining attendance at Cantonese opera performances. Research indicates that children exposed to arts education are more likely to continue attending arts events as adults [38]. Without early exposure to the arts, individuals may miss out on available opportunities and avoid participating altogether. As arts education diminishes in schools, overall attendance may decline over time.

Arts administrators and educators often focus primarily on the preferences of current audience members. However, they should also consider the everyday activities of potential audience members. Individuals engaged in artistic practices in their lives are more likely to attend performances, highlighting the importance of fostering personal engagement in the arts. For instance, self-identified artists frequently attend museums and performances for inspiration. Communities contain individuals with past artistic experiences and a desire to

learn; rekindling these latent interests can benefit arts organizations in the long run.

6.2. Connecting Future Audiences Amidst Changing Times

Considering rapidly evolving social, economic, and technological landscapes, researchers have examined the motivations and habits of younger audience members to identify strategies for enhancing arts participation [39]. New segmentation research on audience psychology, communication preferences, and habits has led to innovative ideas for arts institutions to engage potential attendees and donors. Several studies have explored strategies for cultivating loyal audiences and leveraging social media to build attendance. Adjusting the branding of an arts organization or art form based on audience perceptions can be a complex yet beneficial undertaking. In the context of Cantonese opera, educators and policymakers could explore ways to re-brand the art form, showcasing its beauty to promote performances and ensure cultural continuity.

This study underscores that no single art form can meet the diverse expectations of various audience segments. Audience development encompasses engaging individuals in local communities and broadening participation in arts activities while deepening existing engagement [40]. Effective communication and information dissemination can enhance intrinsic motivation and foster positive attitudes toward the arts [9]. Programming teams within Cantonese opera organizations should consider developing outreach initiatives targeting less frequent attendees and non-attendees. For example, shorter excerpts of performances may be more appealing to younger audiences who might feel daunted by the prospect of attending lengthy shows. Pre- and post-performance activities can also facilitate a better understanding of Cantonese opera for non-attendees.

Planning for audience development necessitates a thorough exploration of marketing strategies. Often, arts organizations allocate significant resources to program development and presentation, neglecting the promotion of awareness and attendance among target audiences. Although effective programming is essential, well-structured marketing plans are crucial to achieving audience development goals [37]. Marketing can drive behavioral changes, while public relations can shift public perceptions. An effective marketing approach involves identifying customer needs and designing strategies to meet those needs. Key elements of the marketing mix include product/service offerings, distribution, pricing, and promotion. While marketing focuses on driving consumption of products and services, public relations aims to enhance visibility and public perception of the organization and its offerings. Arts producers and organizers should develop cohesive marketing and public relations strategies to support overall audience development objectives [37].

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